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Integrating Proactive Work Behavior in Talent Management: Driving Differentiated Employee Behaviors in Dynamic Work Environments. Evidence From Telecommunication Sector

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ABSTRACT

In today's challenging global business environment, organizations are increasingly focusing on fostering proactive employee behaviors to maintain long-term competitiveness. This research explores the impact of talent management (TM) practices on employees' behaviors, emphasizing the moderating effect of proactive work behavior (PWB). Grounded in Self-determination theory, this study posits that investing in the development of high-potential/high performing employees through TM practices yields positive outcomes such as in both in-role, extra-role and adaptive behaviors. Utilizing a sample of 206 differentiated employees from telecom sector organizations, data was analyzed using Partial least square-structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). The findings reveal that TM practices significantly enhance employee behavior. Notably, PWB was found to strengthen the positive relationship between TM practices and extra-role behaviors, but not in the case of in-role behaviors. These insights extend the literature on TM and organizational behavior by underscoring the role of proactive employee behaviors in amplifying the effects of TM on discretionary actions. The study also offers practical recommendations for organizations aiming to optimize their TM strategies to cultivate a proactive workforce and drive organizational success.

Keywords: Talent Management, Proactive work Behavior, In-role Behavior, Extra-role Behavior, Telecommunication Sector.

Introduction

In the aftermath of COVID-19, businesses face a complex, dynamic landscape characterized by volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (VUCA). The telecommunications sector has experienced significant shifts, accelerating digitization and remote work trends, which have transformed organizational structures and task execution (Awadhi et al., 2021). These changes demand a reassessment of traditional business practices, especially in talent acquisition, development, and retention (Caligiuri et al., 2020; Collings et al., 2021). To succeed in post COVID global business environment, organizations must adopt talent management (TM) practices that encourage proactive work behavior (PWB), fostering resilience and adaptability in rapidly evolving environments (Meyers, 2020). TM extends beyond conventional human resource management (HRM) practices, encompassing a strategic approach aimed at leveraging human capital to fulfill organizational objectives (Kraugusteeliana et al., 2023). Effective TM is increasingly acknowledged as a crucial factor in a firm's ability to gain a competitive edge in the market (McDonnell et al., 2021). TM encompasses a range of human resource strategies focused on attracting, selecting, developing, and retaining employees with high potential or exceptional performance (Vaiman et al., 2020). TM differs from general HRM by targeting a select group of high-performing individuals, rather than the workforce as a whole (Collings & Mellahi, 2013). This targeted approach ensures that limited resources are invested strategically in employees who are likely to yield higher returns, enhancing organizational efficiency and performance (Becker & Huselid, 2011). The rationale behind WFD is that evenly distributing resources across all employees can lead to inefficiencies and excessive costs (Collings et al., 2021). WFD reinforces the notion of exclusive TM, therefore, exclusive TM allows firms to optimize their talent pool, ensuring that high-potential individuals contribute to sustaining a competitive advantage in the long run (McDonnell et al., 2023).

In this context, Conventional management approaches, which typically emphasize

employee compliance with directives, are becoming increasingly insufficient in today's rapidly evolving business landscape (Tarique & Schuler, 2020). The global shift to remote work, ignited by the COVID-19 pandemic, has forced businesses to adapt to new work models in order to sustain operations. The telecommunications sector played a crucial role in maintaining global connectivity, while over 80% of businesses faced significant disruptions during pandemic. Despite global widespread halts, the telecom industry remained operational with a new work structure referred as work from home (WFH), supporting essential services through next-generation technologies like 4G and 5G. This transformation in work environments highlights the need for employees to exceed traditional job requirements by demonstrating proactive behaviors, which not only stabilize but also subsidize the dynamic challenges (Lai et al., 2021). In response to post pandemic dynamic challenges, organizations are increasingly reliant on their employees to exhibit proactive behaviors that go beyond their formal job descriptions (Lai et al., 2021). These proactive behaviors, which include taking personal initiative to identify and solve problems, suggesting improvements, and actively influencing their work environment, are critical for organizations to maintain stability and respond effectively to changes in the competitive landscape (Parker et al., 2017). Existing research has highlighted the importance of TM practices in cultivating these valuable employee behaviors.

The telecommunications industry in Pakistan has experienced a remarkable transformation in recent years, significantly influenced by privatization and deregulation efforts. The entry of foreign telecom firms in 2004 has ignited competition, placing immense pressure on organizations to keep pace with rapidly shifting consumer demands and maintain a competitive advantage (Javed & Khan, 2022). In addition, the liberalization policies that introduced next-generation mobile services in 2014 further intensified competition, triggering a "talent war" for exceptional human capital. Despite this heightened competition, the sector continues to face a shortage of skilled professionals, exacerbating the challenge of TM (Mujtaba et al., 2022).

The global shortage of skilled workers poses significant challenges, particularly in developing economies within South Asia. Pakistan is a prominent example of this issue, especially within its telecommunications sector, which plays a pivotal role in driving economic growth and technological advancement. However, the sector faces a multifaceted challenge in TM, where the need for a workforce that is both proficient in current practices and adaptable to future challenges is paramount. The dynamic nature of the telecommunications industry, coupled with rapid technological advancements and evolving consumer demands, necessitates robust TM strategies aimed at enhanced behavioral performance of differentiated workforce.

Despite the increasing focus on TM and its impact on employee behaviors, gaps remain in the literature. While prior research has primarily explored the direct effects of TM on either in-role or extra-role performance, the overall influence on behavior encompassing in-role and extra-role behaviors has been underexplored (Vaiman et al., 2021). Empirical studies are needed to examine how exclusive TM practices impact the overall behavior of a differentiated workforce (Chen et al., 2023). Second, the role of PWB as a moderator has been less explored, there is a need to investigate how TM practices can be optimized to not only improve task-related (in-role) performance but also foster discretionary, change-oriented actions (extra-role behaviors) as highlighted by De Boeck et al. (2018). Third, To the best of the author's knowledge, contemporary literature lacks empirical evidence of PWB as a high-order construct. This study bridges the literature gap through empirical validation of the four forms of PWB. Additionally, this research explores the intermediate effect of PWB as an HOC in the direct

relationship between TM practices and employee behavior, which remained a grey area in TM research. Fourth, most studies have focused on Western contexts, leaving a significant gap in emerging economies such as Pakistan, where cultural and organizational differences might affect the TM -employee behavior link (Chen et al., 2023). Moreover, dynamic work environments, such as the telecom sector, require employees to proactively adapt and contribute to organizational change, yet the interplay between PWB and TM remains underexplored (Tarique & Schuler, 2020). Addressing these gaps could offer valuable insights for organizations aiming to enhance competitiveness through effective TM strategies.

The rest of the study is organized as follows: the second part highlights the theoretical orientation of the study and hypotheses development. The third section depicts the methodology, the fourth part illustrates the results of the study. The final sections elaborate the conclusion and theoretical and practical implications followed by research limitations and future directions.

Theoretical orientation of the study

Self-Determination Theory (SDT) serves as a foundational framework for understanding human motivation, offering profound insights into the forces that drive behavior (Weiner, 1990). Initially focused on the effects of intrinsic and extrinsic rewards, SDT has evolved into a comprehensive macro-theory, addressing a wide range of human behaviors and motivational dynamics (Ryan & Deci, 2020). Beyond its early emphasis on motivation, SDT now informs research in human resource management, organizational behavior, and employee proactivity (Meyers, 2020). In the realm of proactive behavior, SDT provides a robust explanation for how individuals pursue long-term goals with intentionality and foresight. Proactive behavior, aligned with the tenets of SDT, is marked by a spontaneous, future-oriented mindset that seeks change and improvement (Frese & Fay, 2001). This theoretical perspective underscores the interconnectedness of motivation and proactive behaviors, illustrating how individuals navigate their environment with a forward-looking approach. Through this lens, SDT extends beyond motivation to explore how proactive behaviors influence one's interaction with personal goals and future outcomes, revealing its broad applicability in both individual and organizational contexts.

TM practices centered on employee development can be understood as mechanisms that satisfy employees' intrinsic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness, in line with the principles of SDT (Deci & Ryan, 2008). SDT emphasizes that the fulfillment of these needs fosters intrinsic motivation, which plays a critical role in driving positive workplace behaviors. As organizations invest in the development of their employees' talents, they are essentially creating an environment where these psychological needs are met, thereby enhancing intrinsic motivation. This, in turn, leads to improved in-role performance, defined as behaviors that are part of an employee's formal job responsibilities, and extra-role behaviors, which encompass discretionary actions that contribute to the organization's well-being and adaptive behaviors through which employees drive themselves into the dynamic and disruptive changes of the external environment. Employees opt for behaviors that best fit the dynamic situational demands.

PWB, characterized by self-initiated actions and the anticipation of future organizational needs, emerges as a pivotal moderator in the relationship between TM practices and employee performance outcomes (Parker & Collins, 2010). Employees who exhibit PWB are likely to experience an intensified positive effect of TM practices on their in-role, extra-role behaviors and adaptive behavior. This is because the

autonomy and competence associated with PWB align closely with the psychological needs highlighted by SDT, thus further enhancing the motivational impact of TM initiatives. Consequently, this study proposes that TM practices have a positive influence on both in-role and extra-role behaviors, and that the strength of this influence is contingent on the level of PWB demonstrated by employees. Validating these hypotheses empirically would not only contribute to a deeper understanding of the interplay between TM and employee behavior but also provide organizations with practical insights. By incorporating both the motivational and proactive dimensions of their workforce, organizations can better optimize TM strategies to drive enhanced workplace outcomes. This approach, grounded in the theoretical framework of SDT, offers a comprehensive lens for examining the effectiveness of TM practices in fostering enhanced behavioral performance.

Hypotheses Development

Talent Management Practices and Employee Behavior

The relationship between TM practices and employee behavior has become a focal point of organization behavior research, particularly in the post pandemic dynamic and competitive business environments. TM practices, focus on enhancing employees' competencies, skills, and knowledge, with the overarching goal of improving both individual and organizational performance. As organizations face increased challenges in retaining skilled employees, the role of TM as a mechanism for promoting positive employee behaviors has become more critical (Meyers et al., 2020). These practices are essential in fostering employees' ability to adapt to changing work environments, enhancing organizational performance, and encouraging innovation (Chen et al., 2023). TM practices that exclusively focus on employee development, can shape employee attitudes and behaviors. Recent literature highlights the critical role of TM practices in influencing various aspects of employee behavior, including in-role performance, extra-role behaviors and adaptive behavior (Tarique & Schuler, 2020).

In-role behaviors are a fundamental indicator of job performance and are directly influenced by TM practices. Employees who are provided with ongoing development opportunities become more proficient in their job roles, leading to better task performance and overall job satisfaction. According to a study by Boonyarit (2021), organizations that invest in employee development experience higher levels of employee engagement, which enhances task-related performance. Furthermore, such development initiatives often result in employees feeling more competent and capable of handling work-related challenges, leading to increased motivation and better performance outcomes. Recent studies have found that TM practices can positively influence both in-role and extra-role behaviors of employees (Filippus & Schultz, 2019). When employees perceive that their organization is committed to their personal and professional growth through TM initiatives, such as targeted training, mentoring, and career development opportunities, they are more likely to reciprocate by fulfilling their formal job responsibilities to a high degree (Ariyati & Ratnasari, 2021).

TM practices extend beyond influencing in-role behaviors to significantly impact extra-role behaviors, encourage employees to go beyond their formal job requirements and engage in extra-role behavior that benefit the organization (Lai et al., 2021). Extra-role behavior refers to voluntary actions employees take to support their organization beyond formal job requirements. These discretionary actions, such as assisting colleagues or contributing to a positive organizational climate, are often driven by a sense of reciprocity (Choo et al., 2023). Employees who perceive that their organization is invested in their development are more inclined to "go the extra mile" and engage in

extra-role behaviors that benefit the organization (Tarique & Schuler, 2020). TM initiatives create a positive cycle, where employees feel valued and, in return, contribute more proactively to the organization (Collings et al., 2019). Research suggests that when employees are given opportunities for growth, they are more likely to share knowledge and support their peers, fostering an environment of collaboration and continuous improvement. This reciprocal relationship between TM practices and extra-role behaviors strengthens the organizational culture, improving overall performance. In sum, TM practices play a pivotal role in shaping employee behavior across various dimensions, including in-role, extra-role, and adaptive behavior. By satisfying employees' intrinsic psychological needs and enhancing their competencies, TM initiatives foster both immediate and long-term positive behavioral outcomes. Employees who are given opportunities to develop their skills are more likely to perform well in their designated roles, engage in discretionary behaviors that benefit their organizations, and take adaptive steps towards dynamic challenges. As research continues to evolve in this area, it becomes increasingly clear that organizations must prioritize TM as a core element of their TM strategies that fuel enhanced employee behaviors (Meyers et al., 2020; Choo et al., 2023). Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H1a: Talent management practices will have a positive effect on in-role behavior.

H1b: Talent management practices will have a positive effect on extra-role behavior.

Proactive work behavior moderates the relationship between TM practices and Employee Behavior

PWB, defined as the self-initiated and future-oriented action that aims to change and improve the situation or oneself (Parker et al, 2010), can serve as an important moderator in the relationship between TM practices and employee behaviors (Lai et al., 2021). Proactive employees are more likely to recognize and seize opportunities presented by the organization's TM initiatives and leverage these opportunities to enhance their own behavioral performance (Chen & Jun-rong, 2021). PWB has emerged as a key moderator in the relationship between TM practices and employee behavior (Meyers, 2020). Employees exhibiting PWB do not wait for instructions but proactively seek ways to improve processes and outcomes within their organizations (Akhtar & Riaz,2024). Studies have shown that TM practices can enhance PWB by equipping employees with the necessary skills and confidence to take initiative (Meyers, 2020).

In view of the above literature, in summary the relationship between organizationally initiated TM practices and overall employee behavior (in-role and extra role) is significantly moderated by PWB, particularly among differentiated employees. TM practices reinforce the notion of workforce differentiation by allocating resources based on individual potential, that creates an environment where employees are not only encouraged to develop skills but also empowered to take initiative and adapt to changing organizational needs (Tarique, 2021). This study underlines the premise that when Differentiated employees, those identified as high potential or high performing were offered exclusively with development opportunities as formal initiatives by the organization as TM practices, they often exhibit PWB. Thus, it is hypothesized that:

H2a: Proactive work behavior will moderate the relationship between talent management practices and in-role behavior, such that the positive relationship will be stronger for employees with higher levels of proactive work behavior.

H2b: Proactive work behavior will moderate the relationship between talent management practices and extra-role behavior, such that the positive relationship will be stronger for employees with higher levels of proactive work behavior.

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1 Theoretical framework

Methodology

This research adopted a systematic approach to assess the relationships between TM practices, PWB, and both in-role and extra-role behavioral performance of differentiated workforce within the telecommunications sector in Pakistan. To qualify for participation in the study, organizations were required to meet two criteria: (1) they must be registered with Pakistan's Securities and Exchange Commission, and (2) they should have established a formal Human Resources department within the last 3 to 4 years. These criteria ensured that the organizations possessed relevant experience in implementing formal TM policies and practices, rather than relying solely on traditional administrative HR systems. We initiated contact with HR managers at selected telecommunications companies to identify their talented employees. After securing a list of these high performing/high potential employees who were officially got the status of talented employee, questionnaires were distributed via an online platform developed using Google Forms. A total of 206 usable responses were collected from participants. To measure the constructs of interest effectively, the research instrument's face validity was assessed by a panel of five experts, three from the industry and two from academia. This evaluation process allowed us to refine the questionnaire and confirm its appropriateness for addressing the study's objectives.

Measures

Low order Measure

TM practices were assessed using a five-point Likert scale, based on the framework provided by CIPD (2013). This scale has been validated by numerous studies (e.g., Glaister et al., 2017; Raheem & Khan, 2019). Its broad acceptance in research underscores its reliability for evaluating TM practices across various service sector businesses.

In recent TM literature, various methods are utilized to assess these workplace behaviors. For the purposes of this study, the scale developed by Tremblay et al. (2010) was adopted to evaluate the in-role and extra-role behaviors of talented employees. This scale has been widely acknowledged for its effectiveness in capturing employee behavioral reactions within organizational settings.

High-order Measures

Parker and Collins (2010) identified PWB as a high-order construct measured through

four dimensions, which include: Taking charge: This dimension refers to taking initiative and being assertive in making decisions and taking action to improve the work situation. Voice: This dimension refers to using one's voice to express opinions and ideas and to advocate for change within the organization. Individual innovation: This dimension refers to taking the initiative to develop new ideas, processes, or products that improve the work situation. Problem prevention: This refers to taking proactive steps to anticipate and prevent potential problems before they occur. All of these dimensions emphasize taking charge and instigating transformation within the internal organizational setting, whether by new effective ways of doing work or exerting influence over colleagues. To quantify these proactive behaviors, a 13-item, 5-point Likert scale developed by Parker and Collins (2010) is employed. This scale captures the extent to which individuals engage in taking charge, voicing concerns, innovating, and preventing problems, offering a comprehensive tool for assessing PWB of differentiated workforce.

Model Estimation Technique

To estimate the relationships among TM Practices, EBR and PWB (HOC), this study employs Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) as a statistical tool for data analysis. PLS-SEM is particularly suitable for predictive models involving complex higher-order constructs, as formative-reflective construct (Sarstedt et al., 2019). PWB, is a formative-reflective construct, where the second-order formative dimensions (e.g., taking charge, voice, individual innovation, and problem prevention) contribute to the broader latent construct of proactive behavior, Parker and Collins (2010, 2017) highlighted the need to empirically test the multidimensionality of PWB, asserting that its dimensions—taking charge, voice, individual innovation, and problem prevention—are distinct and contribute uniquely to the overall construct. They serve as separate yet complementary dimensions that reflect the higher-order construct of PWB, each playing a critical role in forming the comprehensive nature of proactive behaviors. The inclusion of a second-order construct allows for a more nuanced understanding of how multiple proactive behaviors interact to shape the impact of TM practices on EBR. PLS-SEM was selected due to its robustness in handling complex models with formative-reflective constructs and small to medium sample sizes (Legate et al., 2021). This study employed a two-stage disjoint analysis by following the authors' guidelines (Becker et al., 2022) to evaluate second-order reflective-formative-HOC. In stage one, the estimation and measurement model assessment for the first-order constructs is based on the standard model through convergent and discriminate validity of all reflective-first-order constructs. The higher-order component is not included in the PLS path model. In stage two, the latent variable scores from stage one results help create and estimate the HOC model. The convergent validity of the formative measurement model involves redundancy analysis (Legate et al., 2023). The validity of the first-order reflective constructs was tested through multicollinearity and the significance of outer weight for forming HOC (Becker et al., 2023). The values in Table 3 indicate that the first-order constructs used to assess PWB as HOC are reliable and valid. The VIF values are all below the threshold of 0.5 and the outer weight of all constructs is statistically significant. The redundancy analysis is used to test the convergent validity by examining the correlation between formative identified construct and alternative reflective variables describing the same phenomena.

Data Analysis

Demographic Profile

The demographic characteristics indicate that the sample is predominantly male (77.2%), with a large proportion aged 31-40 years (54.5%). Educational qualifications are varied, but over half (51.5%) have 16 years of education, and 37.1% have completed 18 years. Professional experience is substantial, with 37.6% of participants having more than 12 years, while newer professionals (1-3 years) account for 6.9%. The majority are in permanent employment (76.2%), and most earn between 80,000-160,000 per month (35.1%), with smaller groups in other income brackets. Regarding tenure, many employees have been with their current organization between 1-3 years (19.3%), 3-5 years (19.3%), or over 12 years (19.8%). Hierarchical positioning is heavily skewed toward middle-level management (61.4%), followed by lower-level (15.3%) and top-level roles (10.9%). Executive and technical staff make up smaller portions of the workforce, reflecting a diverse and experienced sample within the organization as depicted in table 1.

Common Method variance (CMV)

Several techniques can be used to detect common method variance (CMV), as outlined by Podsakoff et al. (2003). The most commonly used approach in HRM research to mitigate this issue is to use measurement scales with differing endpoints. To minimize the impact of common method bias, we utilized variable measurement scales with different endpoints. For instance, we measured TM practices using a 5-point Likert scale, while PWB was assessed using a 7-point Likert scale.

Table 1 Demographic profile of respondents

Demographic Characteristics		Frequency	Percent (%)
Gender	Male	156	77.2 %
	Female	46	22.8 %
Age	21 - 30 years	51	25.2 %
	31 - 40 years	110	54.5 %
	41 - 50 years	38	18.8 %
	51 and above	3	1.5 %
Qualification	14 years	21	10.4 %
	16 years	104	51.5 %
	18 years	75	37.1 %
	Doctorate	2	1.0 %
Total Professional Experience	Less than one year	2	1.0 %
	1 - 3 years	14	6.9 %
	3 - 5 years	27	13.4 %
	5 - 7 years	45	22.3 %
	7 - 9 years	13	6.4 %
	9 - 11 years	25	12.4 %
	More than 12 years	76	37.6 %
Employment Type	Contractual	48	23.8 %
	Permanent	154	76.2 %
Monthly Income	40,000-80,000	54	26.7 %

	80,000-160,000	71	35.1 %
	160,000-220,000	34	16.8 %
	220,000-440,000	27	13.4 %
	440,000 and Above	16	7.9 %
Duration in Present Org.	Less than 1 year	30	14.9 %
	1 - 3 years	39	19.3 %
	3 - 5 years	39	19.3 %
	5 - 7 years	33	16.3 %
	7 - 9 years	11	5.4 %
	9 - 11 years	10	5.0 %
	More than 12 years	40	19.8 %
Hierarchical Level	Low level	31	15.3 %
	Middle level	124	61.4 %
	Top level	22	10.9 %
	Executive level	21	10.4 %
	Technical Staff	3	1.5 %
	Any other	1	0.5 %

Table 2 Total Variance Explained.

Factor	Initial Eigen values			Extraction sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	9.605	33.122	33.122	9.018	31.097	31.097

First-order measurement model Assessment

In stage one, TM practices, employee behavior and four first order dimension of PWB were assessed through reflective assessment evaluation procedures suggested by (Hair et al., 2019). Table 3 shows that all the factors have loading above 0.7, demonstrating the reliability of the first-order constructs mentioning the variable's name. Convergent validity was tested through AVE While discriminate validity was ensured through Cross-loading at item level, Fornell–Larcker Criterion and HTMT ratio at construct level (Hair et al., 2019). Table 3, table 4, table 5 and Table 6 demonstrate that first-order constructs fulfil the condition of convergent validity and discriminate validity both for item level and construct level.

Table 3 Validity and reliability of constructs

Construct	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability	Average variance extracted
TMP	0.859		0.504
IR	0.791	0.879	0.710
ER	0.712	0.822	0.537
II	0.862	0.916	0.783
TC	0.882	0.928	0.810

VC	0.890	0.924	0.752
PP	0.816	0.890	0.731

Notes: TMP: Talent management practices. IR: In-role behavior, ER: Extra-role behavior, II: Individual innovation, TC: Taking charge, VC: Voice, PP: Problem prevention.

The reliability and validity of the first-order reflective constructs were further supported by examining multicollinearity and the significance of the outer weights in the formation of the HOC (Sarstedt et al., 2019). The variance inflation factor (VIF) values were well below the critical threshold of 5, indicating no multicollinearity issues. Overall, the redundancy analysis confirmed the convergent validity, reinforcing the robustness of the model and its capacity to represent PWB as a multi-dimensional higher-order construct.

Table 4 Heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT).

	ER	II	IR	PP	TC	TMP	VC
ER							
II	0.606						
IR	0.577	0.501					
PP	0.564	0.882	0.556				
TC	0.553	0.843	0.575	0.846			
TMP	0.341	0.449	0.397	0.350	0.447		
VC	0.595	0.815	0.639	0.747	0.843	0.432	

Notes: TMP: Talent management practices. IR: In-role behavior, ER: Extra-role behavior, II: Individual innovation, TC: Taking charge, VC: Voice, PP: Problem prevention.

Table 5 Fornell-Larker Criterion

	ER	II	IR	PP	TC	TMP	VC
ER	0.733						
II	0.479	0.885					
IR	0.426	0.414	0.843				
PP	0.437	0.748	0.456	0.855			
TC	0.439	0.736	0.480	0.721	0.900		
TMP	0.274	0.392	0.340	0.293	0.389	0.710	
VC	0.477	0.719	0.543	0.649	0.751	0.382	0.867

Notes: TMP: Talent management practices. IR: In-role behavior, ER: Extra-role behavior, II: Individual innovation, TC: Taking charge, VC: Voice, PP: Problem prevention.

Table 6 Cross loadings.

	ER	II	IR	PP	TC	TMP	VC
PP1	0.299	0.587	0.263	0.781	0.557	0.281	0.429
PP2	0.433	0.595	0.478	0.875	0.625	0.193	0.604
PP3	0.373	0.737	0.398	0.904	0.663	0.292	0.608
TC1	0.409	0.657	0.445	0.666	0.922	0.333	0.721
TC2	0.392	0.703	0.461	0.680	0.923	0.366	0.664
TC3	0.384	0.625	0.387	0.598	0.854	0.353	0.643
TMP10	0.140	0.261	0.275	0.187	0.256	0.706	0.301

TMP12	0.161	0.236	0.240	0.203	0.254	0.688	0.262
TMP15	0.191	0.245	0.232	0.220	0.320	0.715	0.277
TMP2	0.255	0.379	0.263	0.309	0.289	0.777	0.318
TMP3	0.166	0.343	0.258	0.244	0.309	0.729	0.258
TMP7	0.214	0.223	0.180	0.143	0.278	0.633	0.221
TMP8	0.153	0.265	0.200	0.178	0.241	0.717	0.231
TMP9	0.267	0.244	0.270	0.144	0.259	0.707	0.287
VC1	0.423	0.584	0.451	0.585	0.600	0.270	0.864
VC2	0.362	0.603	0.406	0.512	0.617	0.337	0.876
VC3	0.439	0.604	0.509	0.523	0.608	0.320	0.883
VC4	0.423	0.693	0.505	0.623	0.767	0.392	0.846
ii1	0.448	0.908	0.387	0.673	0.681	0.378	0.687
ii2	0.402	0.871	0.343	0.685	0.655	0.359	0.601
ii3	0.421	0.876	0.369	0.628	0.617	0.302	0.616

Notes: TMP: Talent management practices. II: Individual innovation, TC: Taking charge, VC: Voice, PP: Problem prevention.

Table 7 Cross Model fit

	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.061	0.205
d_ULS	1.534	16.985
d_G	0.642	1.222
Chi-square	749.784	1168.552
NFI	0.787	0.668

Table 8 Variance inflation factor

	VIF
ER1	1.305
ER2	1.561
ER3	1.347
ER4	1.371
IR1	2.552
IR2	2.556
IR3	1.299
PP1	1.628
PP2	1.924
PP3	2.350
TC1	3.277
TC2	3.261
TC3	1.935
TMP10	1.678
TMP12	1.611
TMP15	1.654
TMP2	1.896
TMP3	1.836
TMP7	1.540
TMP8	1.838
TMP9	1.810
V1	2.433

V2	2.671
V3	2.563
V4	2.005
ii1	2.456
ii2	2.072
ii3	2.160

Notes: TMP: Talent management practices. II: Individual innovation, TC: Taking charge, VC: Voice, PP: Problem prevention.

Second-order measurement model assessment

Proactive behaviors, as viewed from a behavioral standpoint, are influenced by and contingent upon the characteristics of the work environment. Furthermore, these behaviors are subject to modification through the influence of environmental factors. Within the framework of these perspectives, it becomes evident that PWB is a multifaceted construct. Consequently, studying this behavior should not be limited to a one-dimensional attribute but should instead consider a range of interrelated proactive behavior components or sets. Research centered around PWB from this perspective delves into various manifestations of proactive behaviors. It is posited that these behaviors are interconnected, as highlighted in the work by Parker & Wu (2014). As a result, PWB is not limited to a solitary action; instead, it encompasses behaviors that demonstrate proactivity across multiple dimensions or components, a concept emphasized by Bindl and Parker (2010). Prior research, exemplified by studies such as (Zia et al. 2024; Guan & Huan, 2019; Smithikrai, 2022) have primarily examined PWB as a lower-order construct, notwithstanding its recognition as a higher-order construct comprising multiple sub-dimensions. In contrast, this current study has reoriented its attention toward a multidimensional interpretation of PWB, deviating from previous research that analyzed these behaviors in isolation from each other.

Validation of PWB as HOC

PWB was the high-order construct in the study founded on four lower-order constructs: individual innovation, taking charge, voice, and problem prevention. To validate the high-order construct, it is mandatory to consider outer weights, outer loadings, and VIF. The outer loading, as depicted in Table 8, were found to be significant (Hair et al., 2019). The outer loadings are above the threshold of 0.5 for each lower-order construct (Sarstedh et al., 2019). Lastly, the VIF values were less than the threshold value of 5 (Hair et al., 2019). Therefore, collinearity is not an issue in this study. Since all the criteria established are met, PWB as high order construct is validated as shown in Table 8.

Table 9 HOC validation

HOC	LOCs	Outer Weights	T Statistics	P Values	Outer Loadings	VIF
PWB	II	0.076	14.320	0.000	0.837	3.072
	TC	0.208	23.418	0.000	0.880	3.104
	VC	0.519	28.817	0.000	0.933	2.669
	PP	0.313	17.145	0.000	0.857	2.671

Notes: PWB: Proactive work behavior, II: Individual innovation, TC: Taking charge, VC: Voice, PP: Problem prevention.

Hypothesis Testing

H1a evaluates whether TMP has a significant impact on in-role behavior. The results reveal that TM practices have a significant impact on in-role behavior ($B = 0.357$, $t = 6.452$, $p = 0.000$). Therefore, H1a was supported. H1b evaluates whether TM practices significantly impact the extra-role behavior. The results show that TM practices has a significant impact on extra-role behavior ($B = 0.283$, $t = 4.237$, $p = 0.00$). Hence, H1b was supported. H2a tests whether PWB moderates the relationship between TM practices and in-role behavior. The results show that PWB has no moderating impact on in-role behavior ($B = 0.020$, $t = 0.322$, $p = 0.00$). Therefore, H2 was rejected. H2b investigated whether PWB has a significant impact on extra-role behavior. The results show that PWB has a significant impact on extra-role behavior ($B = 0.156$, $t = 1.940$, $p = 0.000$). Hence, H2b was supported.

Table 10 Hypotheses testing

Hypotheses	Relationship	Beta	T value	P value	Decision
H1a	TMP -> IR	0.357	6.452	0.000	Accepted
H1b	TMP -> ER	0.283	4.237	0.000	Accepted
H2a	TMP x PWB -> IR	0.020	0.322	0.374	Rejected
H2b	TMP x PWB ->ER	0.156	1.940	0.026	Accepted

Notes: TMP: Talent management practices, PWB: Proactive work behavior, IR: In-role, ER: Extra role.

Discussion

For this study, the researchers aimed to investigate the relationship between TM practices and differentiated employee behaviors, with a particular focus on the moderating role of PWB. It was hypothesized that TM practices would have a positive effect on in-role, extra-role behavior, and that PWB would strengthen these relationships. (Arocas & Valle, 2022; Chen & Jun-rong, 2021). The research was conducted in the telecommunication industry, which is characterized by a highly dynamic, competitive environment that requires employees to be proactive and adaptable (Arocas & Valle, 2022). Recognizing the need to further explore the mechanisms underlying the relationship between TM practices and employee behaviors, particularly the role of PW. Despite an abundance of studies addressing the conceptualization and significance of TM (Dries, 2013; Gallarado et al., 2016; Meyer 2020; Tansely, 2011), less attention has been given to understanding how behavioral reactions to TM. There is an urgent need for empirical studies that move beyond theoretical assumptions and propositions (Mujtaba and Mubarik, 2022; Thunnissen et al., 2013). Therefore, the study aims to investigate the association between TM practices, employee in-role and extra-role behavior, and PWB as a moderating mechanism which strengthen the relationship between TM practices and differentiated employees' behaviors.

Theoretical Contribution

This research makes significant theoretical contributions by exploring how a behavioral perspective on PWB within TM can drive differentiated employee behaviors in dynamic work settings, specifically in the telecommunication sector. By applying self-determination theory (SDT), the study reveals how employees' intrinsic motivation

fosters diverse behavioral outcomes, leading to both in-role and extra-role performance that aligns with organizational adaptability needs. From a behavioral standpoint, integrating PWB into TM recognizes that not all employees react uniformly to talent initiatives. Instead, their responses vary based on their motivation levels and the degree to which their psychological needs are met—key aspects of SDT. Employees who experience high autonomy, competence, and relatedness are more likely to engage in proactive behaviors that extend beyond their job descriptions. This behaviorally driven differentiation allows organizations to maximize the unique strengths and responses of employees, facilitating tailored contributions in a VUCA (volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous) environment.

Moreover, this study highlights that talent practices supporting PWB can cultivate adaptive and forward-thinking behaviors, moving beyond the conventional one-size-fits-all approach in TM. By identifying how PWB influences employees' capacity for creativity and problem-solving, it emphasizes the value of behaviorally differentiated strategies in promoting innovation and resilience. The research also provides insights into sector-specific challenges, underscoring that in fast-evolving fields like telecommunications, talent strategies that foster behavioral differentiation are crucial for sustaining high performance and organizational agility. This focus on behavioral responses to talent practices broadens the scope of TM literature, positioning PWB as essential to achieving differentiated and sustainable employee behaviors in complex work environments.

Practical Implications

This study highlights actionable insights for HR practitioners in Pakistan's telecom sector, emphasizing how TM initiatives can positively shape employee behaviors, particularly when moderated by PWB. For HR teams, understanding this relationship is critical in designing and implementing effective programs that enhance both in-role and extra-role behaviors, crucial for adapting to the sector's dynamic environment. First, HR practitioners should prioritize TM programs that cultivate essential skills while aligning with employees' career aspirations and growth needs. By providing structured training, mentorship, and career development opportunities, HR can foster an environment where employees feel valued, which positively impacts their engagement and dedication to core job responsibilities (in-role behavior). Telecom sector organizations should incorporate flexible learning paths, enabling employees to learn at their own pace while staying motivated to exceed role expectations. Furthermore, integrating PWB as a moderating factor in TM practices can enhance extra-role behaviors, such as organizational citizenship and innovation. HR can encourage this by implementing supportive structures like collaborative platforms and autonomy in decision-making, allowing employees to go beyond their defined roles. By empowering employees with control over certain aspects of their work, HR fosters an ownership mentality, which promotes proactive initiatives beneficial for organizational growth and adaptability.

HR practitioners should also facilitate a feedback-rich environment where employees receive constructive insights on their PWB and developmental progress. Managers should be trained to recognize and encourage proactive behaviors, thus creating a culture where taking initiative is rewarded. By strategically integrating PWB within TM efforts, HR teams in Pakistan's telecom sector can drive enhanced in-role and extra-role behaviors, positioning the organization to better navigate industry challenges (Akhtar & Riaz, 2024). This approach not only boosts performance but also builds a proactive, resilient workforce that aligns employee growth with long-term business

objectives.

Limitation and Future Directions

This study presents certain limitations, which open pathways for future research. Focusing solely on the telecom sector in Pakistan may limit the generalizability of the findings to other industries. Future research could broaden the scope by examining other sectors comparisons to enhance the external validity of the results. Additionally, as the study relies on self-reported data, there is a risk of response bias. Employing multi-source data collection methods, such as supervisor assessments, could provide a more objective understanding of employee behaviors. The cross-sectional design of this study also limits its ability to establish causality. Future research could adopt a longitudinal approach to capture the long-term effects of TM and PWB on employee behavior over time. Furthermore, this study focuses on PWB as a single moderating factor; exploring additional moderators or mediators, such as organizational support or job autonomy, could offer deeper insights into the mechanisms driving the relationship between TM practices and employee engagement. Expanding these areas would further clarify the impact of TM programs across diverse work environments.

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